

AN ELECTROCARDIOGRAM SYSTEM WITH CONNECTED TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, heart diseases is the leading cause of death worldwide. In order to detect heart diseases and abnormalities in the early stage of the disease progression, a mobile electrocardiogram (ECG) has been developed to record the electrical activities of the heart. The ECG signal has detail information regarding the heart conditions. Monitoring the electrical impulses (ECG waveforms) that travel through the heart in each heartbeat provides direct information regarding the heart functionality. The portable ECG system developed in this study utilizes an ECG sensor module (AD8232), Bluetooth module, FTDI basic breakout, and Arduino Pro mini. The functionality of the mobile ECG prototype was tested using a patient simulator that is able to generate various types of ECG signals. The patient simulator can generate all types of ECG signals including the normal sinus ECG, and abnormal ECG signals such as in arrhythmia and myocardial infarction signals. Android studio software was used for creating the apps for displaying the ECG waveforms on a mobile screen. The ECG signal recorded from the simulator is displayed on the serial monitor of the Arduino sketch, then transmitted using Bluetooth module and finally displayed on the screen through mobile application software developed on the mobile phone. Through this project, ECG signals can be monitored remotely and can be observed by the user from anywhere they want. The developed mobile ECG system can also record ECG signals to be referred to the medical doctors in the future.

Keywords : electrocardiogram, heart rate, connected technology

ABSTRAK

Pada masa kini, penyakit jantung adalah penyebab utama kematian di seluruh dunia. Bagi mengesan penyakit jantung dan irama tidak normal jantung pada peringkat awal, satu peranti elektrokardiogram (ECG) mudah alih telah dibangunkan untuk merakam aktiviti elektrik jantung. Isyarat ECG mempunyai maklumat terperinci mengenai keadaan jantung seseorang. Pemantauan keadaan impuls elektrik (gelombang ECG) yang bergerak melalui jantung pada setiap denyutan jantung memberikan maklumat langsung mengenai keadaan fungsi jantung. Sistem ECG mudah alih yang dibangunkan dalam kajian ini menggunakan modul sensor ECG (AD8232), modul Bluetooth, pelarian asas FTDI, dan Arduino Pro mini. Kefungsian prototaip ECG mudah alih telah diuji menggunakan sebuah simulator manusia yang berupaya mengeluarkan pelbagai jenis isyarat ECG termasuk corak ECG yang normal dan tidak normal seperti dalam keadaan aritmia dan infarksi miokardium. Selain itu, perisian studio Android telah digunakan untuk membuat aplikasi bagi memaparkan bentuk gelombang ECG pada skrin peranti mudah alih. Isyarat ECG yang dirakam dari simulator manusia dipaparkan pada pemantau siri Arduino, kemudian dihubungkan menggunakan modul Bluetooth ke perisian telefon bimbit dan akhirnya dipaparkan pada aplikasi perisian yang dibangunkan di telefon mudah alih. Melalui projek ini, isyarat ECG boleh dipantau dari jauh dan boleh dilihat oleh pengguna di mana sahaja mereka berada. Sistem ECG mudah alih yang dibangunkan juga dapat merakam isyarat ECG untuk dirujuk kepada para doktor dimasa hadapan.

Kata kunci: elektrokardiogram, kadar denyutan jantung, teknologi terhubung

INTRODUCTION

In this recent years, the amount of unknown diseases has been spreading around and can caused many death to mankind. Some of the diseases are caused by the abnormal behavior of the heart. Diseases caused by the abnormalities pattern of the heart are very difficult to be detected and one slight changes in the pattern of the heart can indicate to some kind of dangerous diseases. Because the heart is the center of the human body and cardiovascular disease (CVD) is the major cause of human mortality worldwide. CVD can be presented and also cured.

Heart problem can be tackled if we the number of ECG electrode and home ECG monitoring system is used (Panda et al. 2014)(Azariadi et al. 2016). Other than that, the cardiac monitoring system known as ECG system need to be moved to somewhere within our reach and not available only in the hospitals, The affordability, accuracy and the deep penetration are the key success of the CVD solution (Babu et al. 2018). In order to monitor patient information the mobile health care is needed. Body Sensor Network (BSN) technology will allow some important physiological quantities, such as electrocardiograph (ECG), respiration rate, blood oxygenation (SpO₂),

body temperature, electroencephalograph (EEG) (Pirozzi et al. 2018). So, any problem in the behavioral of the heart is very dangerous and needed to be detected at early stage. So, some devices has been created in order to observe the behavioral of the heart pattern. A device that can detect the electrical activity of the heart is called the electrocardiogram (ECG). ECG is a diagnostic tool displays every details of the electrical activities of the heart (Brucal et al. 2016). A huge amount of training is needed in order to interpret every single pattern of the ECG signal. Numerous amount of studies have been done in order to produce this kind of device and interpretations. With the help of electrodes being placed on the patient body, the ECG can be operates to produce the ECG patterns. A standardized amount of electrodes has been used, ten electrodes are needed to produce 12 electrical views of the heart. An electrodes patch is placed on each arms and leg and the remaining six patches is placed across the chest of the patient. This device is being used in the hospitals and health facilities. In order to operate this kind of device, we need the expertise knowledge such as the doctors or nurses. By using the expertise knowledge, it can cost a huge amount of money. Some people cannot afford to pay for this kind of services. So, an alternative has been developed in order to create a cheaper ECG device for people who has less income to use it.

Since, the primary target of this project is to create a portable and cheap ECG device, it is necessary for the developed device to be small and lightweight so that it can be carried around easily. Early stage detection of cardiac symptoms can be detected by using the real-time acquisition and processing using the wearable biosensors (Domazet et al. 2017)(Tsamis et al. n.d.). Other than that, the hardware chosen to create the devices must considered a few possibilities such as the hardware need to be small and very cheap. By the helps of this system, the device can be portable and the treatments can be obtain in their own places by not going to the local hospitals. By producing this system, the people from the village will be interested to the system (Vignesh 2014). In order to achieve the idea of the device need to be portable the Bluetooth module has been chosen to make the device wireless. An ECG module called AD8232 is used to detect the electrical impulse activities in the heart. Other than that, Arduino Pro mini is the device chosen to program the Bluetooth module and the AD8232 in order to generate the ECG data. The main reason for the Arduino Pro mini to be chosen is because the module itself is very small and lightweight. And it is capable to program the AD8232 without any problem and can generate the signal without any noise in it. Some other problem may interfaced when the transmission of data is being done by the Bluetooth module. Data

transferred from Bluetooth may cause some data losses and some noisy signal may occur.

METHODOLOGY

Firstly, the implementation of the project are divided into three phases. The three phases are research, finding the right hardware and assembling. The beginning of the projects is started with this three phases. The researching part is being done in order to find the most suitable method and the most suitable hardware. A few articles is chosen and the researching parts is accomplished. The next phase is finding the right hardware. The kind of hardware that we need was the hardware must be small, can be carried anywhere and most importantly cheap. This is the few hardware used in order to produce this device which is AD8232, Arduino Pro Mini, FTDI basic breakout, Bluetooth module, resistor and a human simulator. This hardware is decided after a few consideration and the following function are as follows. Basically the AD8232 function is to detect the electrical impulse of the body. Then, the Bluetooth module is for the device to communicate with the application had been made in mobile phones. Other than that, human simulator contains many kinds of ECG signals including abnormal ECG such as any ST elevations, sinus arrhythmia, atrial fibrosis and many more. FTDI basic breakout basically is used to connect the Arduino to the computer. Lastly, a few resistor is used in order to step down the Arduino Pro mini because Arduino Pro mini only operates in 5v conditions but the Bluetooth module need to work in a 3.3v conditions. Basically, the 5V Arduino Pro Mini is being step down the voltage in order it can reach the optimum voltage with the Bluetooth in order for the device to work. After deciding the right hardware, each of the hardware is being assembled and programmed.

From studies of a few document of journal that I have obtained that the choosing of this hardware especially Bluetooth as the communication medium can be managed and the result was pretty successful. But, a few problem can be encountered since the acquired signal is in the form of analog signal. Then in order to convert it we need to use the ADC unit to converts it into a digital signal. The data loss also will be very high and the data will have a few damaged when we transfer the data by using a Bluetooth communication module. Other than that, a huge data loss also can happen if we send the data in the form of analog signal. That's explained the conversion of analog to digital signal (Vignesh 2014). Figure 1 shows the flow diagram of the project. Table 1 and Table 2 list out details for the connection of AD8232 and Bluetooth and connection of Arduino and Bluetooth module, respectively.

Figure 1. Flow Chart

Table 1: Connection AD8232 and Bluetooth

AD8232 CONNECTION WITH ARDUINO	
AD8232	ARDUINO
GND	GND
3.3v	3.3v
OUTPUT	A0
LO-	11
LO+	10
SDN	Not used

Table 2: Connection Arduino and Bluetooth Module

Connection Arduino and Bluetooth Module	
Arduino Pro Mini	Bluetooth Module
VCC	VCC
GND	GND
RX	TX
TX	RX

There are two softwares involved in the process of using the ECG sensor module AD8232. The first software is the Arduino and second one is the Processing software. Arduino software is used in order to program both of the AD8232 module and the Bluetooth module. Besides, the processing software is used to display the ECG signals from the AD8232 in the computer. Basically, the images being displayed in the processing is being transmitted from the AD8232 after the module detected any ECG waveform coming from the user body.

After the proven result can be displayed on the computer we can observe the ECG signal in the computer. The ECG signal is observed then the PQRS peak is determined. If all the PQRS peak is detected then the ECG signal has been proven to be correct and the AD8232 can detect the ECG signal from the body. Next step will be the development of the application on the phones. The development of

the apps is being done by a software called the Android Studio. The application is created in order to display the data that is being received by the Bluetooth to display the ECG signal. The purpose of the application is to display the ECG signal that is being obtained by the human body and save the ECG signal that is being received.

The application will receive the data from the Bluetooth in data form. The data is being exported from the serial monitor of the Arduino. The serial monitor of the Arduino will display a few running numbers that contain each the data points of the ECG signal. The range of the running numbers are between 500 to 800 and the numbers are moving continuously in each second. The data is being transferred using Bluetooth to the application and the running number from the serial monitor is being used to plot each of the point in the application. The concept of plotting is direct plotting data from the serial monitor. And the range of the graph that is being plotted is being set around 500 to 800. The data will be plotted around that range and an ECG signal is being produced. The application also displayed the heart rate reading that is being detected by using the plotting of the data. The application program also calculates the resulting heart beat in units of beats per minute (BPM). The heart rate is calculated as the rate of peak to peak of the R peaks of the ECG signal. Using the sampling rate of 260 Hz, the resulting formula for BPM is as in equation (1).

$$BPM = \frac{60}{(RR \text{ time interval}) \times \frac{1}{260}} \quad (1)$$

The setting of the Bluetooth connection between the Arduino is quite different and a few resistor is used in order to step down the voltage of the Arduino. The voltage of the Arduino is being step down to 3.3v because the operating voltage is around 3.3 v to 5v. In order to synchronize the voltage between the Bluetooth and the Arduino the voltage is being step down by using a few resistor of 1k and 2k resistor. This is being done so that we can match the operating voltage of the Bluetooth. The Bluetooth will not work if the operating voltage is not synchronize and the data cannot be transferred.

In this work the softwares used are Matlab and Coolterm where the Coolterm is used to extract the data from the serial monitor and convert the data into txt files. These txt files will be transferred to Matlab where the data of the ECG signal can be displayed on the computer screen and signal processing can be done using Matlab toolboxes. Similar concept of data transfer is being used to transfer strings of data using Bluetooth to other devices to be displayed on the screen using other specific application platform.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The assembly of the ECG system was successfully done for fundamental testing. Figure 2 shows the hardware setup for this project where the ECG sensors are connected to a patient simulator that generates ECG waveforms. Figure 3 is the ECG waveforms obtained through the ECG circuitry. The stream of numerical values of recorded ECG data and displayed on the serial monitor of the Arduino program is shown in Figure 4. The serial monitor shows the running numbers that are can be plotted into the graph in the application created in the mobile phone. Finally, Figures 5 shows the graph of ECG waveforms being plotted in the application created using Android Studios, with the average heart rate value displayed on the application visualizer.

Figure 2. Mobile ECG basic circuitry connected to a patient simulator

Figure 3. ECG signal in processing software

Figure 4. Serial Monitors of the Arduino

Figure 5. ECG signal displaying on the Applications

DISCUSSION

Initially there was a problem related the Bluetooth module was encountered during circuit testing and development. The Bluetooth module requires a certain level of operating voltage in which it will not transmit data if the voltage is not reached. The Bluetooth module has an optimum operating voltage at 3.3V. Few resistors were used to stabilize the voltage at the working condition. Once the Bluetooth started to work near the optimum voltage, an LED will blink indicating no data is sent. When the Bluetooth is already connected to a device it will start blinking rapidly indicating data is being sent. After finished data sending, the LED will return to blinking back to normal (one blinks in every second).

An ECG patient simulator is used so that circuit testing can be done based on known ECG signals from a more stable source. The patient simulator also helps on learning few kinds of abnormal ECG signal that contain few diseases such as atrial fibrosis, ST depression or elevation and many more. Moreover, using the patient simulator, circuit testing can be done easily because there are no attachment to ECG electrodes pad to a human body, thus the hustle of reattaching of electrode to an actual human subject can be avoided. Furthermore, the ECG data from a real human body contains lots of noise compared to the patient simulator.

The baud rates of the Arduino programming was set to be of the same with the serial monitor of the Arduino baud rates. If the baud rates is not the same it will have a few problem in the connection of serial monitor with Arduino and the serial monitor will not receive any data. The baud rates that is being set used is 9600 baud rate. If the baud rates is set higher or any lower than that value the serial monitor will displays some unknown characters. Then, the connection of the circuits for the Bluetooth connections with the Arduino also needs to be corrects. If the TX and RX of the Arduino is not connected to the RX and TX of the Bluetooth it will not receive any data from the serial monitor of the Arduino. The limitation of Bluetooth connections is

that it can only supports a short range type of communications (Hu et al. 2009).

For the Android studio software, the connection when connecting the application and the Bluetooth need to be stabilize for a few minutes then the results will appear on the screen of the mobile phones. An unknown character is displayed when it is being displayed in the screen computer of the application due to the high sampling rates. A few bug were encountered during application development and testing. Some of the bugs interrupted the application where it will suddenly shut itself off when the results cannot be displayed. Sometimes a bug causes the application to stop running when the connection between the Bluetooth and the application is not stabilize.

When using the Coolterm software, the ports used need to be reset each time after obtaining the data. The data in txt form cannot be obtained if the port is not flushed after using the Coolterm software. If the port is not flush, the next attempt to obtain new data containing txt files can't be created and it will display a notification stating that the port is experiencing an error.

CONCLUSION

From this study, it can concluded that the ECG signal can be recorded by using the ECG sensor module AD8232. The ECG data is sent to a mobile phone using Bluetooth module. A mobile apps for acquiring the ECG signal has been developed for a portable ECG system that can display the ECG system that can display the ECG signals on mobile phones and save the ECG data for future analysis. A problem involving the Bluetooth modules is correlated with the connection system where there is a few problem in transferring the data making the application cannot capture every single number from the serial monitor of the Arduino. This product can be improved by implying a basic signal processing on the ECG signals so that a clean ECG signals can be displayed on the mobile screen with a peak detection that can be enabled to alert any signal abnormalities thus early heart diseases can be detected. Peak detection can detect any different in the PQRS peak then this can be conclude into some kind of diseases then we can determine whether what diseases that the patient is having. Other improvement that can be done is to fix the connection of the Bluetooth and the application so that every single data can be sent without missing out any of the data points. Then, we can insert a few database in the application so that the data is being sent to the application and it can be saved for future analysis or for any future references for the doctor of any health specialist.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This study receives partial financial support from Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia through the university research grant (GUP-2018-050).

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